

RESEARCH PAPER

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Seasonal Variations in Biochemical Composition of Short Neck Clam *Paphia malabarica* from Ashtamudi Lake, Kerala, India

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Abstract

Gross biochemical composition and condition index of short neck clam *Paphia malabarica* was investigated from February 2023 to July 2024. Proteins, lipids and total carbohydrate showed similar patterns of variation according to the reproductive cycles, highlighting the importance of the reproductive cycle and physiological features of the species and also the influence of environmental conditions in determining biochemical composition. Protein and lipids were maximum in the mature clams (533.4 µg/mg and 48.2 µg/mg respectively) and decreased during and after spawning. Carbohydrates increased during summer (126.4 µg/mg in February 2024) and decreased during monsoon. Condition index was influenced by environmental conditions, which further determined the spawning seasons. Condition index was maximum in January 2024 and minimum in June 2024 with an index value of 9.3 and 6.6 respectively.

Keywords: Biochemical composition; Condition index; *Paphia malabarica*; Reproductive cycle; Short neck clam

Introduction

The molluscan meat, especially the meat of bivalves has been regarded as a promising source to meet the protein demand of global population. The meat of the bivalves are good sources for the provision of high-quality protein with all the essential amino acids for the growth and maintenance of human body (Sujatha et al., 2009). In India, the major share of the bivalve production was reported from the State of Kerala (75.8%) from the southwest coast of India, where clams formed 85.3% of bivalve production in the State. The short-neck clam is resourced from the Ashtamudi Lake, one of the Ramsar wetland of international importance. The Lake (lat 8 45' 26" N and long 76 28' 77" E) is located at Kollam district and is the second largest estuary in Kerala with an area of 61.4 sq. km. longitudinally the estuary lies perpendicular to the coastline and is connected to the Arabian Sea throughout the year. The lake plays a vital role in the socio-economic and cultural history of the state and provides livelihood for hundreds of people (Sitaram, 2014). The short-neck clam fishery of the Ashtamudi Lake of Kerala was the first Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) certified fishery of India.

Considering the importance of bivalves as a source of protein-rich food, there has been considerable work on the biochemical composition of commercially important species from all over the world. The knowledge of the biochemical composition of any edible organism is of considerable importance in understanding the physiochemical mechanism which in turn reflects in its nutritive value. Seasonal variations in biochemical composition and physiological condition of organisms occur in relation to energy metabolism necessary for growth and reproduction. It is also strongly related to water temperature, food availability and the gametogenic cycle (Ojea et al., 2004). An

understanding of the biochemical constituents of short neck clam during different seasons would be valuable for sustainable utilization and management of such natural resources.

It is reported that seasonal metabolic activities in molluscs result from complex interactions among food availability, environmental conditions, growth and reproduction (Gabbot, 1975). Studies of energy metabolism are concerned with the ways in which major carbohydrate; lipid and protein fuels are used by an organism to produce energy. As the nutritional and energy demands of marine animals are not constant and are affected by exogenous factors such as food availability and temperature, and by endogenous factors such as energy demands for reproduction, metabolic reserves accumulated in tissues may be used in energy production or converted into various biochemical components (Berthelin et al., 2000). Marine bivalves show seasonal cycles of energy storage and utilization that are closely related to reproductive activity (Giese et al., 1967). Several studies on biochemical cycles in bivalves have been carried out in relation to reproduction (Jayabal, 1994). The general observations have been that the amount of carbohydrate, proteins and lipids increase as gonad development proceeds and then declines following spawning (Robert et al., 1993). In the present study, biochemical composition of whole body of short neck clam *P. malabarica* from Ashtamudi Lake was studied to understand the seasonal changes in nutritive value.

Materials and methods

Materials for the present study were collected for one year period from February 2023 to July 2024 at monthly intervals from Ashtamudi Lake. Temperature and salinity of the lake water were measured during each sampling. The temperature measurements were taken at 0.5 to 1.0 m depth in the water column. The salinity of water samples collected from the sampling sites was estimated by the Mohr-Kundson titration method as given by Strickland and Parsons (1972).

Gametogenic activity

Twenty clams were segregated for histological examination. Gonad tissues from each clam were fixed in Davidson's fixative for 21- 28 hours according to the size of the piece. The tissues were dehydrated in a series of alcohols and embedded in wax. Sections of 7 μ thickness were prepared, stained with haematoxylin and counter-stained with eosin. The different gametogenic stages were then identified in the stained sections according to a modified version of Nagabhushanam and Mane (1975) as maturing, mature, partially spent, spent and indeterminate. When two or more stages occurred simultaneously in a single section, the classification of the stage was based up on the condition of the majority of follicles present in the section.

Condition Index

The shell of 30 clams was opened and soft tissues were shucked out. The tissues and shells were dried at 60°C for 48 hours and weighed to obtain the dry shell weight and dry flesh weight. The condition index was calculated according to Walne (1976) as:

$$\text{Condition index} = \frac{\text{Dry flesh weight (g)} \times 100}{\text{Dry shell weight (g)}}$$

Biochemical analysis

Whole body proximate composition such as protein, lipid and carbohydrate were estimated. Protein content was determined following the method of Lowry et al. (1951), and carbohydrate and glycogen contents according to Dubois et al. (1956). Determination of lipids was done by the sulphophosphovanillin method of Barnes and Blackstock (1973). The results were expressed as micrograms per milligram of dry weight. SPSS version 11.0 was employed to study the ANOVA and correlation of various parameters.

Results and discussion

The mean length of sampled clam population was 26.3 to 32.7 mm. There was variation in temperature following southwest and northeast monsoons and the consequent river discharge. There were two peaks of temperature, one in the pre-monsoon (April-May) and the other in the post-monsoon (December) period. The water temperature ranged between 24.8 \pm 0.4°C (July 2024) to 30.5 \pm 0.6°C (April 2023). The lowest temperature recorded in July-August was due to cloudiness and increased intensity in monsoon precipitation. The water temperature showed an overall significance at 1% level ($R^2=0.921$). The salinity ranged from 16 \pm 0.6 ppt during monsoon (July 2023) to 33 \pm 0.6 ppt during summer (May 2024) and showed an overall significance at 1% level ($R^2=0.933$).

This sharp decrease in salinity during monsoon is due to fresh water runoff during southwest monsoon.

Fig. 1. Maturing male gonad

Fig. 2. Mature male gonad

Fig. 3. Partially spent male gonad

Fig. 4. Spent male gonad

Fig. 5. Maturing female gonad

Fig. 6. Mature female gonad

Fig. 7. Partially spent female gonad

Fig. 8. Spent female gonad

Based on the histological observation, the various gonad maturity stages are represented in Fig. 1 to 8. Fig. 9 represents the percentage of clams in various reproductive stages. The short neck clams showed the onset of gametogenesis in February. This is followed by a period of continuous spawning from March to October. The clams showed minor variations in the condition index with a maximum value of 5.9 in November 2023 and a minimum value (4.8) in April 2023 (Fig. 10). The gametogenic cycle was significantly correlated with the condition index (Pearson product-moment correlation, $r = 0.891$, $p > 0.05$).

The estimation of biochemical composition showed the highest protein value in January 2024 (564.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$). The lowest values were recorded in April and May 2024 (376.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$). Lipid content

was highest during February 2024 (48.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$) and the lowest lipid values were reported in May 2023 (20.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$). The carbohydrate values showed an increasing trend from October 2023 to February 2024 in which the value reached the highest (126.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$). Monthly variation in various biochemical constituents is given in Fig. 11.

Fig. 9. The percentage of short neck clams with various reproductive stages

The fluctuations in the biochemical constituents studied may be interrelated to maturation of gonads and availability of food. In the present study, it was found that compared to other biochemical constituents, the protein values remained high throughout the year. The peak values of protein observed during April-May may be related to the increased biochemical accumulation in gametes, of which protein constitutes the major organic component. The period of low protein values in April-May coincided with the spawning seasons. An increase in the protein content during maturity and a decrease due to spawning has earlier been observed in many other bivalves, such as *Villorita cyprinoides* and *Meretrix casta* (Lakshmanan and Nambisan, 1979), *M. meretrix* (Nagabhushanam and Deshmukh, 1974), *Katelysia opima* (Jayabal, 1994) and *Crassostrea gigas* (Berthelin et al., 2000).

The seasonal variations in lipids showed a similar pattern to that of protein. The lowest lipid values observed coincided with spawning seasons. A similar report has suggested in oysters by Durve and Bal (1961) and in *K. marmorata* by Joshi and Bal (1965). A transfer of lipids from somatic to gonadal tissue may occur, as suggested by the inverse relationship between somatic and gonadal lipid levels observed in *Chlamys opercularis* (Taylor and Venn, 1979). Maximum levels of lipids correspond to the spawning periods, reflecting the fact that lipid is a major component of bivalve oocytes (Holland, 1978).

Fig. 10. Seasonal variation in condition index of short neck clam

Glycogen is the main energy reserve in adult bivalves, being used during gametogenesis and in conditions of nutritional stress. Several workers have reported carbohydrate and glycogen maxima in bivalves immediately preceding and during gamete maturation (Shafee, 1978). An increasing trend in the carbohydrate values coincided with active gametogenesis. In *Crassostrea virginica*, the

carbohydrate level was high in the immature animals and decreased steeply as gametes were formed in the gravid animals (Galtsoff, 1964). High values of carbohydrate and glycogen were reported in *K. marmorata* when the clams remained sexually inactive (Joshi and Bal, 1965). The carbohydrate and glycogen contents were less in *M. meretrix* during the period when mature gametes were present (Nagabhushanam and Deshmukh, 1974). Giese et al. (1967) showed that gonads of *Tivela* had the least carbohydrate storage when mature gametes were present, suggesting a massive conversion of carbohydrates into gamete tissue. The fluctuations in the biochemical constituents of short neck clam are interrelated to the maturation of gonads and the reproductive cycle. The result is further confirmed by the condition index values, which exhibited a similar pattern during the same period.

Fig. 11. Monthly variation in biochemical composition of short neck clam

Conclusion

Gametogenesis is an energy-demanding process, and generally two main strategies of energy utilization are recognized in bivalves. The energy of ingested food can be utilized either directly or indirectly, i.e., by mobilization of storage products synthesized during the growing season. Spawning of *P. malabarica* results in the deprivation of energy stores in the form of carbohydrates and lipids. This is attributed to the utilization of carbohydrate reserves which are believed to occur during periods of stress, such as low salinity rather than to a mere increase in water content. A rapid decline of lipid content in gonads during spawning may be explained by a loss of lipids stored in ripe eggs, while the earlier onset and somewhat slower reduction in carbohydrate content may be due to its increased utilization in the final stages of maturation. Variations in protein content reflect changes in the amount of energy storage compounds; the lowest values coincide with maxima of carbohydrate and lipid contents, and the highest values are attained when these products are utilized. Higher values of protein and lipid during the pre-monsoon period are suggestive of a suitable harvesting period of *P. malabarica*.

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SN conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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